

Studies in the Formation of Schiff Base Complexes. Part I.

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Bis 2-OH-acetophenonimine and methyl derivatives complexes of Cu(II) and Ni(II) have been prepared by treating bis ketone with ammonia and also by reacting metal ammonia complex with the ketones. Ethylenediamine and propylenediamine schiff base complexes have also been prepared by amine exchange from imine complexes. Replacement of ethylenediamine and propylenediamine has also been carried out. The spectra and the magnetic properties of the compounds have been discussed.

THE Schiffbase complexes have been prepared by the reaction of ammonia on the bis-salicylaldehyde complexes of metals¹. Similar studies with 2-OH-acetophenone and its methyl derivatives have not been carried out and were, therefore, considered worth undertaking.

The schiffbase complexes were prepared by using two methods: (1) By refluxing Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes of 2-OH-acetophenone, prepared as reported earlier^{2,3}, with excess ammonia in alcoholic medium.

Where M = Cu(II) or Ni(II).

(2) By refluxing metal amine complex with 2-OH-acetophenone or its methyl derivatives. The reaction can be shown as follows:

Where M = Cu(II) or Ni(II); X = H, 3-CH₃, 4-CH₃, and 5-CH₃.

The Schiff base complexes of ethylenediamine and propylenediamine were also prepared by using first method. The two -NH₂ groups of the diamines undergo condensation with the two ketones resulting in the formation of tetradentate Schiff base complexes.

Where $M = \text{Cu(II)}$ or Ni(II) ; $R = \text{H}$ or CH_3 .

The above complexes were also prepared by refluxing complex-II with ethylenediamine or propylenediamine in alcoholic medium for an hour. Amine exchange takes place resulting in the formation of the diamine schiffbase complex as follows :

Where $M = \text{Cu(II)}$ or Ni(II) ; $X = \text{H}$, 3- CH_3 , 4- CH_3 and 5- CH_3 . $R = \text{H}$ or CH_3 .

Propylenediamine Schiffbase could also be prepared by refluxing ethylenediamine schiffbase complex with propylenediamine.

The solid Schiffbase complexes obtained in each case were washed with water, dried and recrystallised from chloroform. They were analysed for metal and nitrogen contents. The carbon and hydrogen analysis were also carried out in representative cases. Analysis given in Table 1 corresponds with the suggested structures.

The visible spectra of the compounds (300–1000 nm) in chloroform solutions were taken on DU-2 Beckman Spectrophotometer. The IR spectra of the complexes as KBr pellets were obtained in the range 4000–400 cm^{-1} .

The magnetic susceptibility measurements were done at room temperature (28°), using Gouy balance. The magnetic moment values and the characteristic peaks in visible spectrum have been represented in Table 1. The characteristic IR bands have been shown in Table 2.

The compounds, reported in this study, are sufficiently stable at room temperature and in atmospheric conditions. All the Schiffbase complexes obtained are insoluble in water and are soluble in chloroform. They are found to be non-conducting indicating non-electrolytic nature

Most probable structures for all these complexes are square planar. The salicylaldimine Schiffbase complexes are known to be trans in nature⁴⁻⁶. On treatment with ethylenediamine and propylenediamine, there must be a change as $-\text{C}=\text{N}$ groups are on the same side in latter complexes.

The Cu(II) complexes are paramagnetic ($\mu = 1.85$ B.M.), indicating the presence of one unpaired electron. The spectra of Cu(II) complexes exhibit one

broad band at ~ 560 nm as expected for square planar structure. The amine Schiffbase complexes of Ni(II) obtained by treating Ni(II) ammonia complexes with ketones are diamagnetic. Ni(II) ethylenediamine or propylenediamine schiffbase complex obtained by amine exchange from diamagnetic imine schiffbase complex also exhibit diamagnetism.

They have square planar structure. However, the ethylenediamine and imine Schiffbase complexes obtained by direct reaction of bis-2-OH-acetophenone complexes with ethylenediamine or ammonia exhibit slight paramagnetism due to partial polymerisation^{2,3}. The compounds on recrystallization from chloroform become diamagnetic.

In a recent publication, based on a magnetic circular dichroism studies, Kato and Sakamoto⁷ have assigned the low and high intensity bands in Ni(II) square planar complexes to specific electronic transition. The two shoulders at ~ 650 nm and ~ 550 nm are assigned to ${}^1\text{Ag} \rightarrow {}^1\text{B}_{1g}$ and ${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{B}_{3g}$. The high intensity bands at ~ 410 nm and ~ 350 nm are assigned to ${}^1\text{Ag} \rightarrow {}^1\text{A}_u$ and ${}^1\text{Ag} \rightarrow {}^1\text{B}_u$ transition. The spectra of bis ketone complex (I) Bis-(2-OH-acetophenonato) Ni(II) show a band at ~ 650 nm corresponding to ${}^1\text{Ag} \rightarrow {}^1\text{B}_{1g}$ transition. The bis (2-OH-acetophenonimine) Ni(II) complex (II) shows shoulders at ~ 550 nm corresponding to ${}^1\text{Ag} \rightarrow {}^1\text{B}_{3g}$ transition. The other shoulders at ~ 550 nm in the former and ~ 650 nm in the latter are not distinct. The compounds also exhibit two bands at about 350 nm and 410 nm. These have however very high extinction coefficient values ($\epsilon = 5555$, $\epsilon = 4118$). The 350 nm band is also obtained in the spectrum of the free ligand N-N'-ethylene-bis-2-OH-acetophenone. Thus this band in the complex may also be due to the ligand. The band at 410 nm may be due to ${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{A}_u$ transition. The band due to ${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{B}_u$ transition may be merged with the ligand band at ~ 350 nm. The absence of band beyond ~ 600 nm is also a support for square planar structure of the Ni(II) complexes⁸.

Square planar structures or similar Schiffbase complexes of salicylaldimine have been very well established⁹. High extinction coefficient values for the 550 nm band in ethylenediamine and propylenediamine Schiffbase complexes indicates that nitrogen are in cis-position resulting in a structure without centre of symmetry.

TABLE I—MAGNETIC MOMENTS, ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL BANDS AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF Cu(II) AND Ni(II) BINARY SCHIFF BASE COMPLEXES

No.	Name of the complex	Calculated				Analytical data %				Found			Electronic Spectral Bands λ (nm)	Magnetic moment in B.M.	
		Cu or Ni	C	H	N	Cu or Ni	N	C	H	N	C	H			N
1	Bis(2-OH-acetophenone) Ni(II)	17.86	58.41	4.26	—	17.78	58.20	4.46	—	—	—	—	650	86	3.2
2a	Bis(2-OH-acetophenimine) Ni(II)	17.97	58.41	4.89	8.57	18.09	58.56	8.334	8.403	8.403	8.334	8.403	540	92	Partially paramagnetic
3b	N-N'-ethylene Bis(2-OH-acetophenoniminato) Ni(II)	16.64	61.24	5.10	7.94	16.90	61.12	4.978	7.85	7.85	4.978	7.85	560	213	"
4c	N-N'-propylene Bis(2-OH-acetophenoniminato) Ni(II)	16.00	62.17	5.45	7.635	15.61	62.41	5.508	7.891	7.891	5.508	7.891	550	176	Diamagnetic
2a'	Bis(2-OH-acetophenimine) Ni(II)	17.97	58.41	4.89	8.57	18.03	58.25	4.724	8.95	8.95	4.724	8.95	550	88	"
3b'	N-N'-ethylene Bis(2-OH-acetophenoniminato) Ni(II)	16.64	61.24	5.10	7.94	17.08	61.00	5.208	7.752	7.752	5.208	7.752	550	208	"
4c'	N-N'-propylene Bis(2-OH-acetophenoniminato) Ni(II)	16.00	62.17	5.45	7.635	15.90	62.35	5.235	7.524	7.524	5.235	7.524	560	170	"
4c''	N-N'-propylene Bis(2-OH-acetophenoniminato) Ni(II)	16.00	62.17	5.45	7.635	15.88	62.35	5.235	7.281	7.281	5.235	7.281	560	170	"
5	Bis(2-OH-acetophenone) Cu(II)	19.05	57.50	4.197	—	18.75	57.21	3.955	—	—	3.955	—	580	75	1.94
6	Bis(2-OH-acetophenimine) Cu(II)	19.16	57.88	4.82	8.445	19.06	58.00	4.967	8.044	8.044	4.967	8.044	560	70	1.83
7	N-N'-ethylene Bis(2-OH-acetophenoniminato) Cu(II)	17.77	60.41	5.03	7.831	17.95	60.24	5.318	7.938	7.938	5.318	7.938	550	340	1.86
8	N-N'-propylene Bis(2-OH-acetophenoniminato) Cu(II)	17.10	61.36	5.38	7.536	16.68	61.25	5.475	7.435	7.435	5.475	7.435	550	338	1.88
8a	N-N'-propylene Bis(2-OH-acetophenoniminato) Cu(II)	17.10	61.36	5.38	7.536	16.98	61.40	5.285	7.255	7.255	5.285	7.255	550	358	1.88
9	Bis(2-OH-3-Me-acetophenimine) Ni(II)	16.55	—	—	7.89	16.05	—	—	7.856	7.856	—	—	550	103	Diamagnetic
10	N-N'-ethylene Bis(2-OH-3-Me-acetophenoniminato) Ni(II)	15.42	—	—	7.354	15.07	—	—	7.476	7.476	—	—	550	195	"
11	N-N'-propylene Bis(2-OH-3-Me-acetophenoniminato) Ni(II)	14.87	—	—	7.093	14.51	—	—	6.857	6.857	—	—	550	187	"
12	Bis(2-OH-3-Me-acetophenimine) Cu(II)	17.67	—	—	7.787	17.89	—	—	7.484	7.484	—	—	560	81	1.89
13	N-N'-ethylene Bis(2-OH-3-Me-acetophenoniminato) Cu(II)	16.48	—	—	7.262	16.77	—	—	7.117	7.117	—	—	550	382	1.87
14	N-N'-propylene Bis(2-OH-3-Me-acetophenoniminato) Cu(II)	15.90	—	—	7.008	16.01	—	—	7.364	7.364	—	—	550	383	1.94
15	Bis(2-OH-4-Me-acetophenimine) Ni(II)	16.55	—	—	7.89	16.33	—	—	7.621	7.621	—	—	540	96	Diamagnetic
16	N-N'-ethylene Bis(2-OH-4-Me-acetophenoniminato) Ni(II)	15.42	—	—	7.354	15.00	—	—	7.000	7.000	—	—	560	217	"
17	N-N'-propylene Bis(2-OH-4-Me-acetophenoniminato) Ni(II)	14.87	—	—	7.093	14.51	—	—	6.588	6.588	—	—	550	170	"
18	Bis(2-OH-4-Me-acetophenone) Cu(II)	17.57	59.74	4.98	—	17.56	59.50	4.75	—	—	4.75	—	650	52	1.83
19	Bis(2-OH-4-Me-acetophenimine) Cu(II)	17.67	60.07	5.562	7.787	17.50	60.00	5.71	7.525	7.525	5.71	7.525	560	78	1.87
20	N-N'-ethylene Bis(2-OH-4-Me-acetophenoniminato) Cu(II)	16.48	—	—	7.262	16.52	—	—	7.096	7.096	—	—	550	347	1.83
21	N-N'-propylene Bis(2-OH-4-Me-acetophenoniminato) Cu(II)	15.90	—	—	7.008	15.56	—	—	6.908	6.908	—	—	550	320	2.05
22	Bis(2-OH-5-Me-acetophenimine) Ni(II)	16.55	—	—	7.89	16.26	—	—	7.964	7.964	—	—	550	115	Diamagnetic
23	N-N'-ethylene Bis(2-OH-5-Me-acetophenoniminato) Ni(II)	15.42	—	—	7.354	15.75	—	—	7.418	7.418	—	—	560	255	"
24	N-N'-propylene Bis(2-OH-5-Me-acetophenoniminato) Ni(II)	14.87	—	—	7.093	14.84	—	—	6.905	6.905	—	—	560	202	"
25	Bis(2-OH-5-Me-acetophenone) Cu(II)	17.67	—	—	7.787	18.00	—	—	7.78	7.78	—	—	580	74	1.85
26	N-N'-ethylene Bis(2-OH-5-Me-acetophenoniminato) Cu(II)	16.48	—	—	7.262	16.52	—	—	7.563	7.563	—	—	550	370	1.85
27	N-N'-propylene Bis(2-OH-5-Me-acetophenoniminato) Cu(II)	15.90	—	—	7.006	15.88	—	—	7.169	7.169	—	—	550	371	1.83

TABLE 2—THE CHARACTERISTIC INFRARED BANDS OF SOME SCHIFF BASE COMPLEXES OF Cu(II) AND Ni(II)

Complex	-N-H stretch cm ⁻¹	-C-H aroma cm ⁻¹	-C-H aliph. cm ⁻¹	C = O stret. cm ⁻¹	C = N stret. cm ⁻¹	-C-H deform cm ⁻¹	-C-H bending cm ⁻¹	C-O stret. cm ⁻¹	C-C stret. cm ⁻¹	C-N stret. cm ⁻¹	M-O cm ⁻¹	M-N cm ⁻¹
Bis(2-OH-acetophenonato) M(II)	—	3050	2940	1625	—	—	1340	1280	1025	—	660	—
Bis(2-OH-acetophenimine) M(II)	3300	3050	2950 2925	—	1600	—	1340	1280	1025	—	660	590
N-N'-ethylene or propylene bis(2-OH-acetophenonimino) M(II)	—	3050	2950 2915 2900	—	1600	1465	1340	1280	1025	1170	620	590

The more important bands in the IR spectra of the Schiffbase complexes are as follows :

All the spectra show medium absorption at 3050, 3010 cm⁻¹. due to aromatic -C-H stretching. In the bis(2-OH-acetophenonato) M(II) complexes, there are two weak bands at 2940, 2910 cm⁻¹ due to asymmetric and symmetric stretching of the -CH₃ group. These bands continue in the acetophenimine schiffbase complexes. In the ethylene diamine schiffbase complexes and methyl substituted 2-OH-acetophenon complexes, there are additional bands in the -C-H stretching region due to the presence of -CH₂-CH₂- group in the former and additional -CH₃ group in the latter. These compounds also have a band at 1340 cm⁻¹ due to -CH₃ bending and at 1025 cm⁻¹ due to C-C stretching. Ethylenediamine schiffbase complexes have a band at 1465 cm⁻¹ due to -C-H deformation of ethylene bridge. In the amine schiffbase complexes I and II, a sharp band appears at 3300 cm⁻¹ corresponding to -N-H stretching. This band is, however absent in the ethylenediamine or propylene diamine Schiffbase complexes III and IV. The ketonic C = O stretching band at 1625 cm⁻¹ in 2-OH-acetophenone or its bis complexes disappears, and a new band at 1600 cm⁻¹ appears in the schiffbase complexes due to the formation of -C = N bond. The lowering in the -C = N frequency from the free Schiffbase -C = N stretching is due to the coordination of -C = N with the metal. The other bands in the region 1600-1300 cm⁻¹ are due to ring deformation modes. In all the complexes there is a band at 1280 cm⁻¹ due to C-O stretching. In the ethylenediamine schiffbase complexes there

is also a band at 1170 cm⁻¹ corresponding to C-N stretching. The band at 660 cm⁻¹ and 590 cm⁻¹ correspond to M-O and M-N stretching respectively.

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References

1. P. PFEIFFER, E. BUCHHOLZ and O. BAYER, *J. Pract. Chem.*, 1931, 129, 163.
2. D. P. GRADDON and G. M. MOCKLER, *Austral J. Chem.*, 1967, 20, 21.
3. M. W. BLACKMORE, R. W. CATTRALL and R. T. MAGEC, *Inorg. Nuclear Chem., Lett.*, 1968, 4, 305.
4. R. H. HOLM, G. W. EVERETT, JR., and A. CHAKRAVORTY, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 7, 83.
5. S. YAMADA, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1966, 1, 415.
6. S. YAMADA, A. TAKENCHI, K. YAMANOUCHI and K. IWASAKI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1969, 42, 2562.
7. H. KATO and T. SAKAMOTO, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 96, 4131.
8. R. S. DRAGO, "Physical Methods in Inorganic Chemistry", Reinhold, New York, 1968, p. 179.
9. J. M. STEWART and E. C. LINGAFELTER, *Acta Cryst.*, 1959, 12, 842.